

ISic3173

I.Sicily inscription 3173

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S. Lucia

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI329749

1. Ε [— — — — —]
2. □ Ἰησ (οὔς) θε (ός) .
3. μὴ λυπεῖσθε, φίλε·
4. οὐδεὶς ἀθάνατος.
- 5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645503

PHI 329749

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 15.0589

Agnello, S.L. 1955. Recenti esplorazioni nelle catacombe siracusane di S. Lucia. *Rivista di Archeologia Cristiana*. 31: 7-50. At 28 fig.13

Ferrua, A 1989. Note e giunte alle iscrizioni cristiane antiche della Sicilia. Vatican. At no.351

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3173. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388254>